

Streaming data for faster access at a reduced cost

OPeNDAP Services for Data Providers

Summary

OPeNDAP helps organizations and businesses deliver performant data access to their users. Instead of downloading huge files, users can stream just the parts of the datasets they need directly into tools they already use, like Python, MATLAB, R, or GIS software. With OPeNDAP's smart and easy-to-use backend technology, even datasets in outdated formats behave like modern, cloud-native data. This means no extra formatting or bulk downloads, while maintaining high performance at any scale. For any business working with large volumes of data, OPeNDAP can help reduce costs, speed up workflows, and get insights faster — all while keeping cloud data access simple and scalable.

How OPeNDAP can help

OPeNDAP helps organizations and businesses manage large volumes of data, while making the data easily accessible for users. By using streaming technologies, OPeNDAP's solutions make it faster, cheaper, and more efficient for businesses to work with data.

Here's how OPeNDAP can work with your business:

1. OPeNDAP assesses if your data architecture is compatible with an existing OPeNDAP data server, such as our in-house designed [Hyrax server](#), or one of several third-party servers. We also evaluate if the data are structured in a way that makes data access most efficient. The server is run wherever your data are stored.
2. OPeNDAP customizes the data server to address any data that are not immediately compatible, so the server can easily work with your data.
3. OPeNDAP coordinates your existing IT systems and team to ensure the data server runs smoothly.

From here, a user follows this simple process to use your data:

1. The user works within their analysis software of choice, say Matlab, Xarray, ArcGIS R, or OPeNDAP's web-based user interface, to request the parts of the dataset they need. The request takes the form of an OPeNDAP URL.
2. Data are streamed back to the analysis software that the person is using. In this way, data are stored locally on the user's computer while the data are being used and the analysis is occurring. Once the user has their results in hand, the data are automatically removed when the analysis tool stops. Importantly, the entire source dataset was never transferred to the user's computer. Instead, only the subset of data they care about was transferred for a short time, saving the data user time, labor, and space in their computer.

After implementing OPeNDAP's data access approach, your business will simply need to monitor the data server to make sure it keeps working. OPeNDAP will help you build technical capacity in your team, so you can easily add new datasets or fix minor issues. OPeNDAP also provides your business's data users with general support regarding their use of the server and access to your data.

Benefits of using OPeNDAP

While the OPeNDAP approach can work with a variety of data scenarios, it is particularly well suited for grid-like data, such as scientific and geospatial data. Your data users should have some data analysis experience, and be comfortable with common programming languages like Python or Matlab and tools like Jupyter notebooks.

To understand better the benefits of using OPeNDAP, let's look at an example of a data analyst using a 10 TB dataset that covers a global area to develop a decades-long climate model for a specific area. Imagine they only need about 1% of the data in that dataset. Here's a comparison of what it would look like without and with OPeNDAP technology:

Without OPeNDAP, most analysts would download entire files from the cloud, open each file, extract the data of interest, and store the result on their computer. In many cases, the analyst would need to reformat the data and/or write custom software to accomplish those steps. The actual analysis would be yet another step in the analyst's workflow.

Using OPeNDAP, an analyst can stream subsets of data instead of downloading entire datasets. By streaming the data, the analyst works with the data as if it were stored on their computer. No laborious re-formatting of the data is needed.

A comparison of costs to work with a 10TB dataset, where only 1% are actually used:

	Without OPeNDAP	Using OPeNDAP
Download / access time, using a download speed of 1 Gigabyte/sec	28 hours	30 min
Labor time to make data ready for analysis	1 to 2 days on average, although it can take weeks to re-organize and re-format data.	Very little , since data are read in a form that already fits with the analysis tool.
Egress costs (moving data out of the cloud)	\$900 via Amazon Web Services	\$5 , since less than 1% of the data are transferred.

While the egress costs might stand out, the real costs for NOT using OPeNDAP is the extensive labor costs of the analysts. Consider how much 36 hours of an analyst's time costs your business, versus less than 1 hour of their time. In another scenario, whose data would an outside analyst prefer to use? Yours or a competitor with streaming capabilities?

With today's volume and complexity of data, directly downloading entire datasets is no longer practical or wise. OPeNDAP brings data management into the future by providing better ways for data providers to leverage the cloud and streaming technologies.

About OPeNDAP

OPeNDAP is a 501(c)3 not-for-profit corporation and the developer of a suite of open source software tools, including the Hyrax data server and DMR++. OPeNDAP's software facilitates efficient remote data exchange by allowing users to stream subsets of data from large datasets and use data without needing to download and reformat data. OPeNDAP's state-of-the-art technology provides fast and convenient access to data—especially for data stored in the cloud, helping data providers and data users save time and money. Most well-known for their long-time support of NASA's Earth science data system, OPeNDAP's technology is applicable to any data-intensive domain or sector.

To learn more about if OPeNDAP is the right solution for your business, please reach out to us at support@opendap.org.